

Detection

Development of an anti-Imp serological assay for the detection of “flavescence dorée” phytoplasmas in grapevine, insect vectors and host plants

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Abstract

At present serological assays for the detection of “flavescence dorée” (FD), a quarantine disease of grapevine, are not available. The aim of this study was to produce polyclonal antibodies targeting a surface abundant protein of FD and related phytoplasmas, Imp (immunodominant membrane protein), and to verify its use for the detection of FD phytoplasmas in grapevine, other host plant species, and insect vectors. Two antisera were obtained using recombinant Imp proteins from two FD strains. Preliminary results confirmed the specificity and good ELISA performance in the detection of the target in grapevine, clematis and insect vectors tissues.

Keywords: ELISA, grapevine yellows, phytoplasma, serology, leaf hopper

Introduction

Grapevine “flavescence dorée” (FD) is a quarantine disease associated to phytoplasmas and transmitted from grapevine to grapevine by the leafhopper *Scaphoideus titanus* Ball. Control of the spreading of the disease and its vector is mandatory in Europe, and several strategies are suggested, including its early detection in infected plants and insect by means of laboratory analyses. At present the phytoplasma detection is PCR-based since this is a worldwide recognized sensitive, reliable and specific assay, and also due to the absence of alternative reliable diagnostic methods (EPPO, 2016). Serological method development is limited by the low titer of the phytoplasmas in grapevine. Techniques to purify large phytoplasma amounts from herbaceous plants have been exploited to raise polyclonal and monoclonal antibodies (Boudon Padieu *et al.*, 1989, Seddas *et al.*, 1996), however the diagnostic systems were not enough robust for large scale applications. An alternative strategy to obtain a large amount of highly specific antigenic preparations, aimed to raise antisera of improved affinity and sensitivity to the target, and based on recombinant proteins (Liu *et al.*, 2017) was applied. A FD phytoplasma assay based on serology

to perform routine screenings would be particularly useful to ensure a timely detection, or when molecular facilities are not available. Moreover the ELISA test, based on antibodies, is cheaper and easier-to-use than PCR, though less sensitive. The aim of this study was to raise polyclonal antibodies targeting a surface abundant protein of FD and related phytoplasmas, Imp (immunodominant membrane protein), to be used for the detection of this phytoplasma in grapevine, other host plants, and insect vectors.

Materials and Methods

Reference material

FD phytoplasmas used were FD-D and FD-C strains originally collected from Piedmont vineyards. They were obtained from infective *S. titanus* collected alive in the field and allowed to feed on *Vicia faba* in the laboratory. These FD strains were routinely maintained with sequential transmissions from broad beans to broad beans by the experimental vector *Euscelidius variegatus* and by sequential grafting in *Catharanthus roseus*. The *dnaD-imp-pyrG* genomic fragment of FD-D and FD-C (Piedmont) strains were amplified from FD infected grapevine leaves

by nested PCR using primer pair DnaDFDf1/PyrGFDr1 and DnaDFDf2/PyrGFDr2 (patented). A total of 162 amino acids were predicted for full-length FD Imp protein, with residues 44-162 exposed outside the membrane. Two His-tagged partial Imp proteins were synthesized in a *Escherichia coli* system. Each batch was used to immunize two rabbits. The collected antisera, JBA/17 (anti FD-D) and ABA/18 (anti FD-C), were purified by affinity chromatography to prepare IgGs for Western blot (WB) analysis and to prepare two sets of ELISA DAS reagents.

Western blot

Proteins extracted from healthy and FD-C/ FD-D infected periwinkles, broad beans, and *E. variegatus* were used for WB analysis, in order to test the specificity and the functionality of the two antisera.

PCR tests

All samples tested by ELISA were also tested by PCR, using a quantitative protocol (Angelini *et al.*, 2007), and RFLP analysis of the PCR amplified of the 16-23S ribosomal region (Angelini *et al.*, 2001).

Field material

Samples from grapevine (58), *S. titanus* (204), and clematis plants (2) were collected in summer 2018 from known healthy and infected sites, qPCR checked for phytoplasma presence and used for screening the antibody performance.

Results

Expression of the two partial proteins was successful. Titrations of both the antisera were positive in ELISA and in WB against the antigenic recombinant proteins, and confirmed the IgG specificity of both JBA/17 and ABA/18 in infected *C. roseus*, *V. faba*, and *E. variegatus* reference samples. ELISA tests were then carried out for all collected samples. Preliminary data showed an efficient discrimination of the FD-infected and not-infected samples by the two ELISA sets. The JBA/17 showed the best performance, as it was able to detect almost all FD-D-infected grapevines and insects. ABA/18 was able to detect FD-C in infected clematis and insect samples, and in a few grapevine samples.

Discussion

The strategy of producing antisera against the Imp recombinant protein of phytoplasmas has not been used here for the first time. Indeed, Kakizawa *et al.* (2009) produced an antiserum against Imp recombinant protein of OY-W phytoplasma strain; however, this finding was never developed in a kit for routine ELISA detection. In this study, the production of polyclonal antisera against the

recombinant protein targeting FD phytoplasmas and their use in ELISA assays is for the first time reported. Molecular detection of FD phytoplasmas in ELISA-tested field samples is ongoing, with the aim to obtain a full comparison between ELISA and PCR results for the two antisera. Optimization of the protocols for grapevine, host plant species and insect vector sample collection, storage and preparation for serological testing are under study. Once established, the ELISA test for FD phytoplasma will be a valuable tool for routine analyses. Moreover, the developed antisera can be useful for *in situ* studies of FD phytoplasma Imp protein (Trivellone *et al.*, 2019).

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